

DIFFERENCE BETWEEN TRADITIONAL CLASSROOM AND CONSTRUCTIVIST CLASSROOM

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to the role of Constructivism in education, particularly in foreign language learning. The traditional methods of teaching English as a second language have drawbacks. In this regard, constructivist ways of teaching may fill the gaps.

Key words: constructivist approach, traditional classroom, constructivist classroom, predisposition, student-centered.

There are several theories that are applied in education such as behaviorism, cognitivism, constructivism etc. Many educators especially teachers use the theories in the classroom based on their own roles. Each theory has its own different function and purpose and also has a little bit correlation with each other, for example behaviorism theory. In this theory, the teaching learning process focuses on the students centered not the teacher's one. It means that, if the teacher applies it in the classroom, it tends to create the passive students. They just absorb the knowledge from their own teachers. [3, pp175-180]

Constructivism theory is the response to the behaviorism theory. It means that the role of constructivism theory is in the opposite of behaviorism. The students' role is to construct their own understanding and knowledge of the world through experiencing things and reflecting on those experiences. It means that the students construct the meaning of certain thing by assimilating and accommodating through their own experience. It tends to create the active students. While the constructivist teachers encourage and guide the students in order to assess the activities which help

them to get the understanding . The way the teacher guides the students can be conducted through questioning them in order it can create the situation in which the students construct the meaning of thing by themselves. Moreover the function of questioning is to regard the students as the expert learners.

The other function of constructivism theory is it can create problem solving, if the students find problem, they can discuss with other friends to get the solution. That is the point of view about constructivism theory. The next session will be the description of constructivism through the history, definition, types, principles, implementation in teaching learning process, the characteristics of learning, the characters of learners, strength and weaknesses, differences of constructivism with other theories and the comparison between traditional to the constructivist one.

A constructivist classroom is learner-centered, students are active learner and not just recipient of information, the teacher facilitate and guides students to learning. On the other hand, a traditional classroom is more on direct instruction and teacher-centered. Students are passive learner and its the teacher that directs and controls most of the learning activities. [3, pp181-192]

Here is the list of the difference between a traditional and constructivist classroom

Traditional Classroom:

- students are passive learners
- emphasis is more on the basic skills
- textbooks are the main resource
- learning is rote memorization and repetition
- teacher-centered

Constructivist Classroom

- students are active learners
- emphasis on big concepts
- has other sources of materials

- learning is interactive and there is exchange between students and teacher
- learner-centered

In a constructivist classroom learning is more on thinking and understanding and not just merely on rote memorization. Students in a constructivist classroom are curious and ask questions, they enjoy learning in having a part in the exchange of ideas. It not only promotes learning but also promotes social and communication skills. [3, pp181-192]

In a traditional classroom, an invisible and imposing, at times, impenetrable, barrier between student and teacher exists through power and practice. In a constructivist classroom, by contrast, the teacher and the student share responsibility and decision making and demonstrate mutual respect. The democratic and interactive process of a constructivist classroom allows students to be active and autonomous learners. Using constructivist strategies, teachers are more effective. They are able to promote communication and create flexibility so that the needs of all students can be met. The learning relationship in a constructivist classroom is mutually beneficial to both students and teachers. [2, pp273-278]

A Constructivist Classroom is a Student-Centered Classroom. The student-centeredness of a constructivist classroom is clearly apparent in a reader response approach to literature. Recognizing the significance of the unique experiences that each reader brings to the reading of a selection of literature, the teacher in a response-centered approach seeks to explore the transaction between the student and the text to promote or extract a meaningful response (Rosenblatt, 1978). This places the student in a central position in the classroom since exploring this transaction seems unlikely to occur unless the teacher is willing to relinquish the traditional position of sole authority, thereby legitimating the unique experiences that all members of the class bring to the reading rather than just those experiences the teacher brings.

The resulting perception and effect in the classroom is evident in students' recognition that the discussion is a legitimate one involving questions to which nobody knows the answer. It isn't a treasure hunting game where they are trying to guess what is in their teacher's head, but a process that creates meaning and knowledge.

From a constructivist perspective, where the student is perceived as meaning-maker, teacher-centered, text-centered and skills-oriented approaches to literature instruction are replaced by more student-centered approaches where processes of understanding are emphasized. In a discussion of language arts instruction based on constructivist theories of language use and language development, Applebee (1993) suggests that rather than treating the subject of English as subject matter to be memorized, a constructivist approach treats it as a body of knowledge, skills, and strategies that must be constructed by the learner out of experiences and interactions within the social context of the classroom. In such a tradition, understanding a work of literature does not mean memorizing someone else's interpretations, but constructing and elaborating upon one's own within the constraints of the text and the conventions of the classroom discourse community. [1.p 200]

Constructivist teaching is an exceptionally interesting and exciting way to teach because students are involved in learning activities they appear to enjoy, and much more student-teacher contact is possible. It extends one's impact as a teacher.

Constructivism and Language Teaching

The foundation of a constructivist approach as:

1. about constructing knowledge, not receiving it
2. about thinking and analyzing, not accumulating memorizing
3. about understanding and applying, not repeating back

4. being active, not passive. (Marlowe & Page, 2005)

Constructivist learning has developed as a substantial approach to teaching. During past decades many researchers and scientists had elaborated on the historical precedents for constructivist learning theory. In this view constructivism represents the shift from education based on behaviorism, to education based on cognitive theory. [4]

Thus, behaviorist epistemology essence is based on intelligence, domains of objectives, levels of knowledge and reinforcement, however in the case of constructivist epistemology it is the learners who construct their knowledge on the basis of interaction with the environment.

The primary message of constructivism is that active learning enables the students to construct their own knowledge and make their own meaning of what is being thought.

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